

LOPHANTHUS ANISATUS (BENTH) ANALYSIS OF QUERCETIN CONTENT IN THE AERIAL PARTS

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Relevance: According to the data reported in the literature, the raw material of lophanthus anisatus (Benth.) exhibits immunomodulatory activity and contributes to faster recovery from complications of pneumonia, bronchitis, and bronchial asthma. The aerial parts of lophanthus anisatus (Benth.) contain flavonoids, among which quercetin occupies a prominent position. Quercetin is classified as a vitamin P compound and is recognized as a potent antioxidant.

Research Aim: Determination of quercetin in lophanthus anisatus (Benth.) using High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC).

Materials and Methods: The object of the study was the aerial parts of lophanthus anisatus (Benth.), cultivated in 2024. The plant raw material was collected in accordance with generally accepted pharmacognostic requirements and dried in a shaded area. To identify the flavonoids in the plant material, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) was employed. The analysis was carried out using an 'Agilent 1260 Series' HPLC system (Agilent Technologies, USA). The analysis was performed on an Agilent 1200 C18 column (4.6 mm inner diameter, 150 mm length, 5 μ m particle size). The mobile phase consisted of 0.3% orthophosphoric acid (A) and methanol (B). Detection was carried out at 370 nm, corresponding to the characteristic absorption maximum of quercetin. The flow rate of the mobile phase was 1 mL/min, with an injection volume of 10 μ L, and the column temperature maintained at 40 °C. The total run time of the analysis was 20 minutes.

Results:

1-figure. Chromatogram of quercetin (ISN)

2-figure. Chromatogram corresponding to quercetin in Lophanthus anisatus (Benth).

As can be seen from the chromatogram presented above (Figures 1 and 2), the retention time of the quercetin standard sample, determined using a UV detector at a wavelength of 371 nm, was 11.623 minutes.

Conclusions: The aerial parts of *lophanthus anisatus* (Benth.) exhibited a characteristic chromatographic peak for quercetin at a wavelength of 371 nm with a retention time of 11.472 minutes, which corresponded to that of the working standard solution. This finding confirms the presence of quercetin in the plant raw material. The quantitative determination revealed that the quercetin content amounted to 19.8 mg/g.